

Effect of carbofuran application on leaffolder incidence, Aduthurai, India, 1982-83.

Treatment	Leaffolder damage (%)
Control	27.1
0.5 kg carbofuran ai/ha incorporated at planting	24.5
0.5 kg carbofuran ai/ha topdressed at 15 DT	21.1
0.75 kg carbofuran ai/ha incorporated at planting	26.4
0.75 kg carbofuran ai/ha topdressed at 15 DT	19.7
1.0 kg carbofuran ai/ha topdressed at 15 DT	17.6
CD	NS

to subplots in 3 splits – 50% basal, 25% at active tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. Leaffolder incidence on 10 hills/plot was recorded at 60 DT by counting the total and damaged leaves and calculating the percentage.

Method of carbofuran application did not significantly influence leaffolder incidence. However, topdressing of carbo-

Effect of nitrogen level on leaffolder incidence.

furan at 15 DT caused a slight decrease in the pest incidence (see table). Increased levels of nitrogen application caused a

corresponding increase in pest population (see figure). Carbofuran-nitrogen interaction was not significant. □

A new predaceous beetle of whitebacked planthopper in India

B. C. Shukla, S. K. Shrivastava, D. J. Pophaly, U. K. Kaushik, R. K. Agrawal, and Rajeev Gupta, Zonal Agricultural Research Station, College of Agriculture, Raipur 492006 (M. P.), India

Whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) is a potentially destructive rice pest during kharif in Madhya Pradesh. Populations are suppressed by several enemies including mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*. Staphylinid beetle *Paederus fuscipes* Curtis (Staphylinidae: Coleoptera) is a predator of brown planthopper (BPH) in Malaysia, Japan, Taiwan, and Thailand. Two species of this beetle, *P. fuscipes* and *P. melampus* Er., feed on BPH in India.

Large populations (25-30 beetles/hill) of staphylinid beetle *P. fuscipes* were found in fields in Apr 1981, feeding on WBPH nymphs. In confinement the beetles also preferred nymphs. This is the first record of *P. fuscipes* in M. P., India. □

Attraction of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* to light sources

S. Mohan and R. Janarthanan, Agricultural Entomology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai, India

Gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) is a major rice pest in India and in Tamil Nadu State. Infestations occur from Aug to Feb with maximum populations between Sep and Nov. Gall midge attraction to different light sources and light traps

was studied at the Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai. A bamboo trap with a 40W incandescent bulb, a bamboo trap with a 250W infrared lamp, and a Robinson type trap with a 125W mercury vapor lamp were set up in a triangle over the field. The trap positions were randomly interchanged each day after morning counts. Total weekly gall midge catches were combined over 4 weeks and compared.

The bamboo trap with 250W infrared light source attracted the most insects, followed by the 40W incandescent light

Attraction of rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* to different light sources, Madurai, India, 1981.

Week ending	40W incandescent lamp	250W infrared lamp	125W HPL mercury vapor lamp
19 Sep 81	149 (2.17)	360 (2.56)	69 (1.84)
26 Sep 81	120 (2.08)	258 (2.41)	35 (1.54)
3 Oct 81	140 (2.15)	274 (2.44)	67 (1.83)
10 Oct 81	155 (2.19)	255 (2.41)	52 (1.72)
Total	(8.59)	(9.82)	(6.93)
Mean	(2.15)	(2.46)	(1.73)

^a Figures in parentheses are transformed values.